

Unicode Encoding Proposal for the Indus Script – Early Draft

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Abstract

The Indus script is not deciphered yet. There is no consensus on what is and what is not a character. It is likely that many new characters will emerge in future excavations. Despite its aim of universality, *the Unicode Standard considers writing systems for which insufficient information is available to enable reliable encoding of characters to be out of its scope*. We are not at the stage where we can make a proposal for Unicode Encoding for the Indus script. We may not get there for decades to come. In the meantime, we still need some kind of a common encoding for people to record and share text. This section will outline a proposal for an encoding in the *Private Use Area (PUA)* of the *Unicode Basic Multilingual Plane (BMP)*. The hope is that in the future this can be leveraged to an RFC to the community that defines what Unicode calls a "*Private Agreement*". This will allow the community to agree upon a shared encoding and enable tools and technology like fonts and IMEs. This is an **Early Draft** of the proposal. Much of it will only make sense when one can read the words and texts of the Indus script. I will publish a decipherment separately. In the absence of a bilingual inscription, we have no authoritative source to determine the validity of an interpretation. This paper describes a general method to do so based on the fit to data. The upcoming decipherment meets these criteria. The following proposal and discussion are based on this decipherment and may be somewhat cryptic to read until it is available. I humbly ask your patience in this regard.

Keywords: indus script, unicode encoding, proposal, semantics, bidi, collation, akhyats, compounds, phono-semantic compounds, canonical sequence, canonical order

Quick Summary

This proposal defines the range U+E8FF to U+F1AF in the Unicode BMP for the Indus script.

- a proposed Character Encoding Table (Appendix A)
- size of range: 2,225
- number of Characters defined: 638
- number of Characters reserved: 1587

This proposal attempts to conform to or enable the following *Design Principles of Unicode*:

- **Characters, not glyphs:** It specifies character encodings, not glyph forms.
- **Stability:** Once assigned, cannot be reassigned and key properties are immutable.
- **Logical order:** Articulating the default for memory representation.
- **Specification of Bi-directional (Bidi) text handling**
- **Efficiency:** Focuses on making Unicode text simple to parse and process.
- **Plain text:** It represents plain text not rich or structured text.
- **Universal repertoire:** The Unicode Standard provides a single, universal repertoire.

This proposal does not address or considers **out of scope** the following:

- Semantics: so that characters have well-defined properties.
- Unification: unifying duplicate characters within scripts across languages (e.g. Egyptian Hieroglyphs)
- Dynamic composition: accented forms to be dynamically composed.
- Convertibility: guaranteeing convertibility with other standards.
- Unicode Character Database and formal semantics
- Tailorings for Unicode Common Locale Data Repository (CLDR)
- Specification of Collation methods or weights.
- Emoji

Background

The Indus Script has survived to us in the form of seals with relatively short inscriptions of 4-5 characters. The earliest seals discovered so far come from about 3,500BC but the majority are from the Mature Harappan Period of 2,600-1,900BC. Only a few thousand seals have been found till date, out of which 40% of the seals have an illustration apart from text, of those more than half are that of a Unicorn bull. There is no long-form script available to us.

This relative scarcity of information has made it difficult to decipher the script. Unlike Egyptian Hieroglyphs which had the Rosetta stone and Cuneiform which had the Behistun inscription, there has been no bilingual inscription discovered so far. In its absence, we have no way

to learn from someone who knew. Any attempt to decipher the script, including the current one, is a guess that may or may not be correct. There is no logical way to eliminate possibilities down to a single one.

Farmer et al. suggest that the Indus script was not a script (Farmer et al., 2004). Among a number of arguments, they make two statistical arguments to support this. They say that the inscriptions are too small compared to other known languages and that there were too many "singleton" characters (characters that occur just once in the whole corpus).

It is important to point out that these points are neither necessary nor sufficient to conclude that this is not a script. In many ways, the Indus seals are quite similar to Japanese hankos or personal seals. Hankos are used to sign contracts or authorize bank transactions. Most hankos range between 2-4 characters and are enough to serve an economy of the scale of Japan.

Figure 1

A comparison of Japanese and Indus scripts

Description	Indus	Japanese
Inscriptions	4,615	8,850
Corpus Size	16,678	26,040
Unique Characters	585	1,507
Average Length	3.61	2.94
Singletons	33.85%	25.95%

(a)

(b)

(c)

As an example, if we were to take the train station names across Japan and make "seals" of them, we would get about 8,850 names as in Figure 1(a). This is somewhat comparable to the 4,615 Indus seal inscriptions in the Indus corpus. We find that each seal in Japan would, on the average,

have about 3 characters, whereas the corresponding number is closer to 4 in the Indus case. The modern script is actually more terse. This is not surprising because it has a greater number of unique characters. Both have a large number of singletons, although the Indus script has a slightly higher number at 33.85% vs. 25.95%. It is important to note that even in the Japanese case, *for random samples of 4,615 names we get an average of 31.65% singletons*. As we see in Figure 1(b) and 1(c), their relative character distributions also have similar long tails.

The Japanese corpus has 1,507 unique Kanjis versus the 586 unique characters in the Indus. While the Japanese number is larger, it does represent the full range of place names of one of the largest economies, more than an order of magnitude greater in population compared to the Indus and a much later stage in the evolution of the script - i.e. the literature available in Japanese today and the complexity of what it represents is considerably greater than the Indus script would have had in its time. Even though such metrics cannot represent the complexity of either script, but all things considered, they are surprisingly comparable.

Characters, not glyphs

Unicode considers characters to be the smallest component of a written language that has semantic value. As an example, a given character or piece of text may be written in multiple fonts, each of which can have very different appearances, but they all represent the same text, the same characters. So when you search for a word, you don't need to remember or specify what font you wrote it with, just the word because the text is represented in characters, not glyphs. It is the character that receives a Unicode code.

There are two major kinds of scripts in broad use - phonetic scripts and ideographic scripts. Phonetic scripts, like the alphabet, represent sounds and we write a word by how we hear it. In a logographic or Ideographic script, like the Han characters of CJKV (Chinese-Japanese-Korean-Vietnamese) scripts, a character represents a meaning. They generally have one root meaning and retain their semantic content across linguistic boundaries. Instead of understanding what text means by hearing it, we can recognize it by seeing it. It gives communication a visual metaphor.

The Indus script is Ideographic. The characters encode meaning. It is peculiar that even as far as today we do not have a name for these characters. I will call them **Akhyats**. “Akhyat” in Sanskrit means "that which brings to cognition" or “announced, named”. The more familiar “Vikhyat” means “famous or easily recognized” and comes from the same root.

Akhyats are in many ways like CJKV ideographs, and like them, they were most likely used to encode multiple languages. In fact, this is also why Indus inscriptions are terse. They need fewer characters. Unlike a phonetic script like the alphabet where two characters can at most represent 26x26 (676) combinations, in an ideographic script like the Indus, two characters could potentially represent (638x638) more than 400,000. In a CJKV script this number is many orders of magnitude larger. Like any script, not all combinations are valid, but there is no doubt that one needs fewer ideographs to specify the same word compared to phonetic characters.

Figure 2

Different Akhyats versus different glyphs

One of the primary tasks to create a Unicode encoding of Akhyats is to define what an Akhyat is. When do two glyphs mean the same thing and when do they not. In Figure 2 (a), the top shows the same Akhyat in different glyphs or styles found across the corpus. In the bottom we see different Akhyats that look similar but are different. Akhyats can often look quite different without any change in its semantic content and yet can look very similar and mean something different. This

can sometimes be reasonably obvious to see, but many times it is not. In Figure 2(b) we see the many widely varying Akhyat counts from different studies because of this (Possehl, 2002).

The only way to reliably define the set of Akhyats in the Indus script is by reading them. One needs a decipherment. In the absence of a bilingual inscription, in the absence of an authoritative source telling us what the Akhyats meant, any attempt at listing them is an interpretation. It is a guess, and guesses can be wrong. We need some way to validate whether one is right.

There is a way to do this. We create a dictionary definition for all Akhyats at once. We then see if we can meaningfully read all the seals and inscriptions given this definition. If the Akhyat's glyph drawing also happens to convey the same meaning, it is further confirmation, but oftentimes the match is not specific. Han characters evolved into abstract strokes that are unambiguous rather than remain pictograms with many potential interpretations.

Although such a dictionary definition is not guaranteed to be unique or correct, in practice it is incredibly difficult to do. It is not easy to "fit" a set of meanings so that one can read all the text. When it occurs, even in part, such an assignment is quite robust and changes very slowly. If the set of seals that one can read crosses 50% of the corpus, this stability is not likely to be a coincidence. If it further provides reasonable explanations for known facts and gives verifiable and/or verified predictions of things not known, it becomes **a generic methodology to validate a decipherment even when there is no authoritative source.**

In its essence, this method is inspired by the way a machine learns in AI. We are, in effect, trying to fit a model to the data. It is more like a scientific theory than a "logical" argument. And unlike many arguments that selectively focus on some elements while ignoring the rest, this addresses all of them, all the time. It can give surprisingly good results when it finds a good fit.

But it can only speak to validity, not truth.

Using this, if two glyphs occur in roughly the same contexts and mean roughly the same, they may be the same Akhyat, even if they are written in different glyphs. Similarly, if the same

Akhyat reads differently across too many contexts, it is possible that it corresponds to more than one Akhyat and we might be missing something subtle.

The above method does not prescribe how one finds a reasonable mapping in the first place, only the means to evaluate it. I have spent over 10 years attempting to decipher the script and for the past 4 years I have been able to read more than 80% of the Indus characters and published seals. This interpretation represents a large-scale attempt to do the above.

The definition of Akhyats in this proposal is based on this "decipherment". But it is by no means normative. Although the bulk has not changed for years, every time I go through the corpus, I discover things I missed or got wrong. And there is always a chance of a breakthrough needing large scale changes. One of the Design Principles of Unicode is **Stability**, that once a character is assigned it cannot be reassigned, its definition must be immutable (*Submitting Character Proposals*, 2016). This is a high bar. We are not there yet, and we are not going to get there any time soon. This proposal is a Private Agreement and can afford to change. The hope is that over time we will get to a definition stable enough to consider a formal Unicode proposal.

We are choosing to use the PUA of the Unicode Basic Multilingual Plane for this. We have a choice of three possible PUAs, one in the BMP and two larger areas in Plane 15 and 16 respectively. We are going with BMP because we do not need the larger space and BMP is more likely to have support in older e-readers and devices/software. We are reserving a range of 2,225 codepoints and is about the same order as Joyo Kanji (2,136) which is a normative list from the Japanese Ministry of Education to define the minimum requirement to get into college (*Joyo Kanji*, 2023). We have assigned 638 so far, but this has been done with enough headroom to accommodate future Akhyats that we discover as well as establish areas for legacy characters to provide compatibility with or deprecate. While one would like to create a safe playpen to "*Fail fast, fail often, learn and try again*", the truth is that any change may be disruptive to texts that have already been written in a previous version. This needs to be managed in terms of *Versioning and Deprecation* and *Backward Compatibility* where possible. Ideally, one wants a slow-moving target.

Direction of Writing and Unicode BiDi

Figure 3

The Indus Script is strongly Right-to-Left.

Word	Freq	Reverse	Freq
"◊"	174	◊"	5
"⊗"	90	⊗"	4
U	145	U	3
𑀓𑀔𑀕	40	𑀕𑀔𑀓	1
U𑀔	45	𑀔U	3
𑀔𑀕	14	𑀕𑀔	0

(a)

(b)

(c)

Note: The Seal Images are taken from (Marshall, 1931)

One of the aspects of the Indus script where there is relative consensus among scholars is the direction of writing (Mahadevan, 1977). It is Right-to-Left for the most part. This is apparent in some seals where the sculptor ran out of space as they went to the left, as we can see in the seal of Figure 3(b). It is even more evident in Figure 3(c) where the text wraps Right-to-Left, Top-to-Bottom, and then Left-to-Right; where the bottom line is written upside down and is the only place in all the corpus where these Akhyats are upside down. The table shows some of the most frequent words in the script and there is an overwhelming preference for one direction. The last line in the table shows the first two Akhyats of the seal of Figure 3(c). Thus means these characters were read Right-to-Left. The third line, also in the seal, is also in the same Right-to-left direction. The Right-to-Left direction

quickly extrapolates across the entire corpus from the strong direction preference and the reading direction in this seal.

There are actually four separate possibilities for the direction of writing in the corpus:

- Right-to-Left: e.g. 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻
- Left-to-Right (Mirrored): e.g. 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻
- Left-to-Right (Symmetric): e.g. 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻
- Left-to-Right (Shuffled): e.g. 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻

It is important to note that all four directions are merely different visual representations of the same underlying text. 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻, 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻, 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻 are the same sequence of characters. We can render all of them within standard Unicode through the proper choice of direction and mirror forms. This should cover all currently available inscriptions.

Right-to-Left is the most common pattern but we find Left-to-Right as well as mirror or not mirrored forms.

1. Right-to-Left: 94.2%
2. Left-to-Right: 5.8%
 - Mirrored: 2.7%
 - Symmetric: 2.7%
 - Shuffle: 0.4%

Unicode standardizes the Logical order of Characters in the text. This is the sequence of the characters in memory. Essentially this is how we store our text in a file, how algorithms like search match text and many other things. The specification says that we should store the characters similar to how we would enter them on a keyboard. In the case of the Indus script this would be Left-to-Right. We would type 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻 as ① 𑀮 ② 𑀲 ③ 𑀳 ④ 𑀺 ⑤ 𑀻. 𑀮𑀲𑀳𑀺𑀻 is the sequence that would be stored on file as well as made available to all programs. The text rendering directionality would be implemented by Unicode's standard BiDi algorithms.

way. **We must follow Unicode standard right from the start** regardless of the teething difficulties we may have with limited support for the PUA encoding.

Canonical Decomposition

An Akhyat corresponds closest to an Ideograph in the CJKV sense but there are punctuation characters, digits and digit-like characters, and perhaps most importantly compounds, sometimes similar to the phono-semantic compounds in CJKV and sometimes not.

First of all, there are rare instances where the Indus script is used phonetically where each Akhyat represents a single phonetic character. Perhaps the most famous of these is the Dholavira

signboard (Zubair, 2016): which is an example of phonetic usage. Unlike

abjads like the original Phoenician script, here both vowels and consonants are represented as well as long and short vowels are distinguished. The semantic characteristic of the Akhyat is not completely lost in such usage. The Akhyats chosen are “poetically related” in meaning with relation to the word but they primarily represent sound. The same name in Akhyats would be written with two Akhyats. In this inscription, it is interesting to observe that the Akhyats are in their proper Right-to-left direction even though the text itself is written from Left-to-Right. It is tempting to think the Akhyats face you as you read them and in 99% of the inscriptions they do, but they don’t in this one.

There are some other examples as like and others. But less than 1% of the inscriptions discovered so far are used in this phonetic way. For the rest of this proposal we will ignore them and focus on outlining Akhyats that are ideographs.

Figure 4

Compounds in the Indus Script

Unicode distinguishes between base characters and those that are derived from the combination of other characters. As an example, in Figure 4, we find an accented e which has a different Unicode code than e or its accent but is essentially a "precomposed" character. Unicode defines a canonical decomposition into its constituents such that two strings may be compared reliably. These normalized decompositions are defined for all such precomputed characters. There is another kind that is found in Indic and complex scripts where two characters combine to form a new glyph but this precomposed form is not assigned a Unicode codepoint. Instead it is handled by the font and rendered on the fly. There are well-defined rules for such composition that typically come from the language itself and encoding them with codepoints would unnecessarily use up many thousands of slots.

In CJKV scripts base forms combine to form a new character that is assigned a separate Unicode codepoint. In the third line of Figure 4 we have the Han character for "tear", like a tear drop, which is composed from the characters of "water" and "to stand". While the composition is poetically formed from the other two characters there is no doubt it is a separate meaning. One character contributes the core meaning from which the final character is derived and the other

Let us take the bottom two lines in Figure 4. $\text{𑀓}=\text{𑀓}+\text{𑀔}$ can we canonically break this compound down into those two Akhyats whenever we encounter them? Are they canonically equal to the compound Akhyat? Interestingly for this Akhyat it may well be true. This is generally not the case. There are only 2 inscriptions where we encounter the two constituent Akhyats separately. 206 times they are precomposed into the compound, so effectively, the Indus scribes had already precomposed them.

The same is not true of the second example $\text{𑀓}=\text{𑀓}+\text{𑀔}$. The compound occurs only 41 times in the corpus whereas the constituents occur separately 68 times like in $\text{𑀓}||\text{𑀔}$. In actual fact, it is not possible to combine the two Akhyats into the compound in this case because it would completely change the meaning. A rough analogy of this can be seen in English. "computer science" is different from "science computer" so the sequence order matters; this is guaranteed by the Logical order of Unicode. But, is "(computer science) department" the same as "computer (science department)" - most probably not. This combination is not merely dependent on sequence adjacency but has a longer range correlations to a broader context. As an "algebra" it is neither "commutative" nor "associative".

Indus compounds cannot be canonically decomposed, in the Unicode sense, to its constituent base Akhyats. They must be assigned separate codepoints. I suspect this is generally true for all Ideographic scripts.

This is not to say that having a representative decomposition is not useful. As an example, a search engine may want to enrich indus text to match components, like a search for 𑀓 should match both 𑀓 and 𑀓 . But when we encounter compounds in the Indus script, like the phono-semantic case, they have a meaning that is different from the mere composition of its base Akhyats, and need a separate Unicode codepoint to represent them. "computer science" means something specific and different from an "intersection" of "computer" and "science". From this perspective they are similar to Han characters and we can treat them exactly in the same way. In fact, it almost feels like the

phono-semantic nature of Han characters is a natural and later stage of evolution from what we see in the Indus.

A Road to Canonical Order

How do you sort Indus text? This is a matter of great significance. Without the "alphabetical order" it would be hard for us to search for books in a library or even look up a word in a book's index. One could argue that the "Qwerty" system is more efficient in some ways but having a generally accepted scheme has a value independent of the value of the scheme itself. Indeed, there can be multiple competing orders but it is important to have one widely adopted, a universal order. It is likely that the ordering of the Akhyats in the Unicode encoding will be the defacto universal order.

Unlike the ordering in a script with a few dozen characters where any order can do, a script with several hundred or thousands needs to be well-thought through. In the Indus case this has immediate relevance because in the absence of IMEs that can convert phonetic input to the corresponding character, we have no option but scrolling through a list of all of them every single time we want to input one.

In the 2nd century AD, Xu Shen organized the first etymological dictionary he called *Shuowen Jiezi* by selecting 540 radicals, the semantic component of a phono-semantic compound (*Shuowen Jiezi*, 2023). This served as the basis for partitioning the dictionary. As an example, the character for "tear" in the Figure 4 would be listed only under the "water" radical.

Mei Yingzuo's 1615 dictionary *Zihui* made two further innovations. He reduced the list of radicals to 214, and arranged characters under each radical in increasing order of the number of additional strokes – the "radical-and-stroke-count". This method is still used in most present-day dictionaries.

While the number of Akhyats discovered so far is much less, in the hundreds rather than tens of thousands for Han characters, it is still enough to make search non-trivial and memorizing a linear order impractical. One cannot really use the "radical" method as the use of phono-semantic

compounds were not as wide spread. Also, there is much more visual information in the Indus glyph that was abstracted away in the later Han characters as that script grew more complex. But the idea of classes or grouping based on related meaning can find a similar expression in the Indus case.

Etymology Classes and Systematic Polysemy

This proposal partitions the space of Indus Akhyats into **108 Etymology Classes** as in Appendix B. The classes are derived from commonality based on meaning. There are a few large blocks, grouping the classes themselves. The **U block** is essentially the "tomb of the unknown character". In any inscription, where the character is missing or damaged or we simply cannot read it, we use this character to specify that the character is not known. The **N block** is organized based on numbers although the Indus used numbers for various purposes in the script. The **P Block** corresponds to Akhyats related to peoples in the Indus civilization. The **G Block** organizes Akhyats related to places or geographies. The **PxG Block** is a set of place names that are associated to a people as France is to the French. The **O Block** contains various other groupings. Each of these classes have considerable headroom to incorporate new Akhyats while maintaining the same overall order.

It is hard to describe Etymology classes without explaining what each means. A full explanation of this section will need to wait for the decipherment book to be published. But the logic being used may be visible just from the glyph forms to a limited extent. As an example, the four Akhyats 𑀓𑀔 𑀓𑀕 𑀓𑀖 𑀓𑀗 in block P-7 are obviously related. All the classes in the N-Block (N1 to N18) have a similar relationship based on the numbers they represent. In general, various compounds are grouped according their corresponding base form like 𑀓 𑀔 𑀕 𑀖 𑀗 𑀘 𑀙 𑀚 𑀛 𑀜 𑀝 𑀞 𑀟 in G-22. Phono-semantic compounds like 𑀓𑀔 𑀓𑀕 𑀓𑀖 𑀓𑀗 𑀓𑀘 𑀓𑀙 𑀓𑀚 𑀓𑀛 𑀓𑀜 𑀓𑀝 𑀓𑀞 𑀓𑀟 are grouped according to the semantic component rather than the sound component 𑀓. This has the added benefit of distributing them over a number of blocks instead of clustering them in one. It is important to realize that unlike the Han dictionaries phono-semantic compounds do not have the same level of either systematic or standardized use in

the Indus script. Block P-6 𑀧𑀭𑀮𑀯𑀰𑀱 clusters phono-semantic compounds based on their sound rather than radical and I suspect this is indeed how the Indus viewed them because the most important Akhyat in their glyphs is the sound component. In the case of noun compounds, like 𑀧𑀭𑀮, we organize it by the narrower component, in this case by 𑀭 instead of 𑀧. This is like cataloging "Brooklyn Bridge" under "Brooklyn" rather than "Bridge" because it would be easier to find in things related to Brooklyn rather than all things "bridges". It is important to note that the narrower category is defined semantically rather than by frequency of usage. 𑀭 is found in 447 inscriptions rather than 𑀧 which is found only in 147. Appendix C has a breakdown of the Base Forms, Compound Forms and Phono-Semantic Compound forms in the Indus script.

I realize that this is a cryptic and incomplete description. I will come back to this once my decipherment book is published and explain each element in detail. But this is to give a flavor of the kind of considerations went into the design of the Etymology classes. There is no one right answer. Most of it comes from what kind of organization that was useful in finding Akhyats to input in texts.

There is another form of natural organization that is present in the Indus. This is Systematic Polysemy. Systematic Polysemy occurs in various forms in many languages. In English the word "rabbit" can mean both the animal as well as its meat. This is used systematically to generate similar related meanings across a number of words related to animals like chicken, fish, rabbit, lamb, etc. Similarly, the Indus script uses various glyph transforms to generate a form of systematic polysemy. This does not really have a counterpart in the more abstract Han characters. There are the following types - **Chiral Forms**, **Bent Forms** and **Black-and-White Forms**. You can find a listing of each type in Appendix D.

Let us take 𑀧𑀭𑀮 versus 𑀧𑀭𑀮. The central Akhyat of each is a reflected image of the other. These are called Chiral forms. They are different Akhyats but very closely related to one another. They really differ in just one aspect. In a sort, we would ideally like to have these two right next to

one another. We achieve this by placing them in the same Etymology Class as well as right next to one another. This allows for the standard unicode encoding itself to sort them together. So everywhere we encounter Chiral forms we place them together. Everywhere there is a reasonable possibility that a chiral form may emerge in the future, we leave a gap in the encoding to accommodate it. The same is true of Bent Forms like 𑀓 𑀔 and of Black-and-White forms like 𑀕 𑀖.

Naturally, the proposed encoding will allow one to sort Indus text in a Universal Canonical order based on these Etymology classes and this order will be available to all software by default. In effect, it is the same as the alphabetical order in English. But it is important to remember that this is just one order. Just to end out the section on a Canonical Order, the following is taken from the Unicode standard for collation and applies just as well to the Indus case.

- Collation is one of the most performance-critical features in a system.
- Collation is not code point (binary) order.
- Collation is not aligned with character sets or repertoires of characters.
- Collation is not a property of strings.
- Stability is a property of a sort algorithm, not of a collation sequence.
- Collation order is not preserved under concatenation or substring operations, in general.

Versioning, Deprecation and Backward Compatibility

As our understanding of the Indus script evolves this encoding will need to evolve as well. This is an Early Stage Draft and will likely change in the coming weeks and months. Also, while this proposal is my best effort to create a reasonable encoding, it can be wrong. As I engage with the community and they have had chance to reflect their needs into this, newer and better methods of organization may emerge. We need a method to incorporate change until the requirements for change begin to subside. To put some method in the madness, I propose the follow versioning scheme.

Currently everything is pre-release meaning it does not have a version. It is given "as-is, where is" and everything can and will change. I am bootstrapping this over my various projects so as

to get to a reasonable initial state. Even after release of my decipherment and for a time that the community feels necessary this will continue in this pre-release state until people have had a chance to study it and engage with it.

Once released, versioning will start from 1.0.0 and go monotonically upwards. All versions will be retained in a central site. Each version should ideally release a corresponding font (where necessary) so that the community can see the change. Versioning is divided into **major.minor.point** releases.

A **major release** is one where we have breaking changes, which means that an existing character is changed - moved, deleted, etc. Every such character will be moved to a well-defined code in the **Deprecation Block O-6** and people can "search-replace" such characters in existing texts so that they continue to be readable. People may also be able continue using a previous version by embedding the corresponding font.

A **minor release** is one where new characters are added without affecting any existing character. This means that all existing texts can continue without change and any software may upgrade to the new characters, if necessary.

A **point release** means that there is no change in the character assignments but something else has changed and should not affect any existing documents or applications.

Since the versioning explicitly allows for breaking changes, backward compatibility can only be offered to a limited extent through the Deprecation block. Tools and even texts can note what version they require. People should consider embedding an equivalent font so that a text written will continue to be readable where appropriate.

This proposal is merely a suggestion to provide a starting point for discussion. Please feel free to get in touch and suggest improvements or changes.

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Appendix A

Unicode Character Table

															e8ff
															59647
e900	e901	e902	e903	e904	e905	e906	e907	e908	e909	e90a	e90b	e90c	e90d	e90e	e90f
")	'													
59648	59649	59650	59651	59652	59653	59654	59655	59656	59657	59658	59659	59660	59661	59662	59663
e910	e911	e912	e913	e914	e915	e916	e917	e918	e919	e91a	e91b	e91c	e91d	e91e	e91f
			=												
59664	59665	59666	59667	59668	59669	59670	59671	59672	59673	59674	59675	59676	59677	59678	59679
e920	e921	e922	e923	e924	e925	e926	e927	e928	e929	e92a	e92b	e92c	e92d	e92e	e92f
59680	59681	59682	59683	59684	59685	59686	59687	59688	59689	59690	59691	59692	59693	59694	59695
e930	e931	e932	e933	e934	e935	e936	e937	e938	e939	e93a	e93b	e93c	e93d	e93e	e93f
59696	59697	59698	59699	59700	59701	59702	59703	59704	59705	59706	59707	59708	59709	59710	59711
e940	e941	e942	e943	e944	e945	e946	e947	e948	e949	e94a	e94b	e94c	e94d	e94e	e94f
59712	59713	59714	59715	59716	59717	59718	59719	59720	59721	59722	59723	59724	59725	59726	59727
e950	e951	e952	e953	e954	e955	e956	e957	e958	e959	e95a	e95b	e95c	e95d	e95e	e95f
59728	59729	59730	59731	59732	59733	59734	59735	59736	59737	59738	59739	59740	59741	59742	59743
e960	e961	e962	e963	e964	e965	e966	e967	e968	e969	e96a	e96b	e96c	e96d	e96e	e96f
59744	59745	59746	59747	59748	59749	59750	59751	59752	59753	59754	59755	59756	59757	59758	59759
e970	e971	e972	e973	e974	e975	e976	e977	e978	e979	e97a	e97b	e97c	e97d	e97e	e97f
59760	59761	59762	59763	59764	59765	59766	59767	59768	59769	59770	59771	59772	59773	59774	59775
e980	e981	e982	e983	e984	e985	e986	e987	e988	e989	e98a	e98b	e98c	e98d	e98e	e98f
59776	59777	59778	59779	59780	59781	59782	59783	59784	59785	59786	59787	59788	59789	59790	59791
e990	e991	e992	e993	e994	e995	e996	e997	e998	e999	e99a	e99b	e99c	e99d	e99e	e99f
59792	59793	59794	59795	59796	59797	59798	59799	59800	59801	59802	59803	59804	59805	59806	59807
e9a0	e9a1	e9a2	e9a3	e9a4	e9a5	e9a6	e9a7	e9a8	e9a9	e9aa	e9ab	e9ac	e9ad	e9ae	e9af
59808	59809	59810	59811	59812	59813	59814	59815	59816	59817	59818	59819	59820	59821	59822	59823
e9b0	e9b1	e9b2	e9b3	e9b4	e9b5	e9b6	e9b7	e9b8	e9b9	e9ba	e9bb	e9bc	e9bd	e9be	e9bf
								())	—		+	+	+
59824	59825	59826	59827	59828	59829	59830	59831	59832	59833	59834	59835	59836	59837	59838	59839
e9c0	e9c1	e9c2	e9c3	e9c4	e9c5	e9c6	e9c7	e9c8	e9c9	e9ca	e9cb	e9cc	e9cd	e9ce	e9cf
59840	59841	59842	59843	59844	59845	59846	59847	59848	59849	59850	59851	59852	59853	59854	59855
e9d0	e9d1	e9d2	e9d3	e9d4	e9d5	e9d6	e9d7	e9d8	e9d9	e9da	e9db	e9dc	e9dd	e9de	e9df
59856	59857	59858	59859	59860	59861	59862	59863	59864	59865	59866	59867	59868	59869	59870	59871
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59872	59873	59874	59875	59876	59877	59878	59879	59880	59881	59882	59883	59884	59885	59886	59887

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59888	59889	59890	59891	59892	59893	59894	59895	59896	59897	59898	59899	59900	59901	59902	59903
ea00	ea01	ea02	ea03	ea04	ea05	ea06	ea07	ea08	ea09	ea0a	ea0b	ea0c	ea0d	ea0e	ea0f
59904	59905	59906	59907	59908	59909	59910	59911	59912	59913	59914	59915	59916	59917	59918	59919
ea10	ea11	ea12	ea13	ea14	ea15	ea16	ea17	ea18	ea19	ea1a	ea1b	ea1c	ea1d	ea1e	ea1f
59920	59921	59922	59923	59924	59925	59926	59927	59928	59929	59930	59931	59932	59933	59934	59935
ea20	ea21	ea22	ea23	ea24	ea25	ea26	ea27	ea28	ea29	ea2a	ea2b	ea2c	ea2d	ea2e	ea2f
59936	59937	59938	59939	59940	59941	59942	59943	59944	59945	59946	59947	59948	59949	59950	59951
ea30	ea31	ea32	ea33	ea34	ea35	ea36	ea37	ea38	ea39	ea3a	ea3b	ea3c	ea3d	ea3e	ea3f
59952	59953	59954	59955	59956	59957	59958	59959	59960	59961	59962	59963	59964	59965	59966	59967
ea40	ea41	ea42	ea43	ea44	ea45	ea46	ea47	ea48	ea49	ea4a	ea4b	ea4c	ea4d	ea4e	ea4f
59968	59969	59970	59971	59972	59973	59974	59975	59976	59977	59978	59979	59980	59981	59982	59983
ea50	ea51	ea52	ea53	ea54	ea55	ea56	ea57	ea58	ea59	ea5a	ea5b	ea5c	ea5d	ea5e	ea5f
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ea60	ea61	ea62	ea63	ea64	ea65	ea66	ea67	ea68	ea69	ea6a	ea6b	ea6c	ea6d	ea6e	ea6f
60000	60001	60002	60003	60004	60005	60006	60007	60008	60009	60010	60011	60012	60013	60014	60015
ea70	ea71	ea72	ea73	ea74	ea75	ea76	ea77	ea78	ea79	ea7a	ea7b	ea7c	ea7d	ea7e	ea7f
60016	60017	60018	60019	60020	60021	60022	60023	60024	60025	60026	60027	60028	60029	60030	60031
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60032	60033	60034	60035	60036	60037	60038	60039	60040	60041	60042	60043	60044	60045	60046	60047
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eac0	eac1	eac2	eac3	eac4	eac5	eac6	eac7	eac8	eac9	eaca	eacb	eacc	eacd	eace	eacf
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60128	60129	60130	60131	60132	60133	60134	60135	60136	60137	60138	60139	60140	60141	60142	60143
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60192	60193	60194	60195	60196	60197	60198	60199	60200	60201	60202	60203	60204	60205	60206	60207
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60208	60209	60210	60211	60212	60213	60214	60215	60216	60217	60218	60219	60220	60221	60222	60223
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60240	60241	60242	60243	60244	60245	60246	60247	60248	60249	60250	60251	60252	60253	60254	60255
eb60	eb61	eb62	eb63	eb64	eb65	eb66	eb67	eb68	eb69	eb6a	eb6b	eb6c	eb6d	eb6e	eb6f
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eb70	eb71	eb72	eb73	eb74	eb75	eb76	eb77	eb78	eb79	eb7a	eb7b	eb7c	eb7d	eb7e	eb7f
60272	60273	60274	60275	60276	60277	60278	60279	60280	60281	60282	60283	60284	60285	60286	60287
eb80	eb81	eb82	eb83	eb84	eb85	eb86	eb87	eb88	eb89	eb8a	eb8b	eb8c	eb8d	eb8e	eb8f
60288	60289	60290	60291	60292	60293	60294	60295	60296	60297	60298	60299	60300	60301	60302	60303
eb90	eb91	eb92	eb93	eb94	eb95	eb96	eb97	eb98	eb99	eb9a	eb9b	eb9c	eb9d	eb9e	eb9f
60304	60305	60306	60307	60308	60309	60310	60311	60312	60313	60314	60315	60316	60317	60318	60319
eba0	eba1	eba2	eba3	eba4	eba5	eba6	eba7	eba8	eba9	ebaa	ebab	ebac	ebad	ebae	ebaf
60320	60321	60322	60323	60324	60325	60326	60327	60328	60329	60330	60331	60332	60333	60334	60335
ebb0	ebb1	ebb2	ebb3	ebb4	ebb5	ebb6	ebb7	ebb8	ebb9	ebba	ebbb	ebbc	ebbd	ebbe	ebbf
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60352	60353	60354	60355	60356	60357	60358	60359	60360	60361	60362	60363	60364	60365	60366	60367
ebd0	ebd1	ebd2	ebd3	ebd4	ebd5	ebd6	ebd7	ebd8	ebd9	ebda	ebdb	ebdc	ebdd	ebde	ebdf
60368	60369	60370	60371	60372	60373	60374	60375	60376	60377	60378	60379	60380	60381	60382	60383
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60384	60385	60386	60387	60388	60389	60390	60391	60392	60393	60394	60395	60396	60397	60398	60399
ebf0	ebf1	ebf2	ebf3	ebf4	ebf5	ebf6	ebf7	ebf8	ebf9	ebfa	ebfb	ebfc	ebfd	ebfe	ebff

ec00	ec01	ec02	ec03	ec04	ec05	ec06	ec07	ec08	ec09	ec0a	ec0b	ec0c	ec0d	ec0e	ec0f
60416	60417	60418	60419	60420	60421	60422	60423	60424	60425	60426	60427	60428	60429	60430	60431
ec10	ec11	ec12	ec13	ec14	ec15	ec16	ec17	ec18	ec19	ec1a	ec1b	ec1c	ec1d	ec1e	ec1f
60432	60433	60434	60435	60436	60437	60438	60439	60440	60441	60442	60443	60444	60445	60446	60447
ec20	ec21	ec22	ec23	ec24	ec25	ec26	ec27	ec28	ec29	ec2a	ec2b	ec2c	ec2d	ec2e	ec2f
60448	60449	60450	60451	60452	60453	60454	60455	60456	60457	60458	60459	60460	60461	60462	60463
ec30	ec31	ec32	ec33	ec34	ec35	ec36	ec37	ec38	ec39	ec3a	ec3b	ec3c	ec3d	ec3e	ec3f
60464	60465	60466	60467	60468	60469	60470	60471	60472	60473	60474	60475	60476	60477	60478	60479
ec40	ec41	ec42	ec43	ec44	ec45	ec46	ec47	ec48	ec49	ec4a	ec4b	ec4c	ec4d	ec4e	ec4f
60480	60481	60482	60483	60484	60485	60486	60487	60488	60489	60490	60491	60492	60493	60494	60495
ec50	ec51	ec52	ec53	ec54	ec55	ec56	ec57	ec58	ec59	ec5a	ec5b	ec5c	ec5d	ec5e	ec5f
60496	60497	60498	60499	60500	60501	60502	60503	60504	60505	60506	60507	60508	60509	60510	60511
ec60	ec61	ec62	ec63	ec64	ec65	ec66	ec67	ec68	ec69	ec6a	ec6b	ec6c	ec6d	ec6e	ec6f
60512	60513	60514	60515	60516	60517	60518	60519	60520	60521	60522	60523	60524	60525	60526	60527
ec70	ec71	ec72	ec73	ec74	ec75	ec76	ec77	ec78	ec79	ec7a	ec7b	ec7c	ec7d	ec7e	ec7f
60528	60529	60530	60531	60532	60533	60534	60535	60536	60537	60538	60539	60540	60541	60542	60543
ec80	ec81	ec82	ec83	ec84	ec85	ec86	ec87	ec88	ec89	ec8a	ec8b	ec8c	ec8d	ec8e	ec8f
60544	60545	60546	60547	60548	60549	60550	60551	60552	60553	60554	60555	60556	60557	60558	60559
ec90	ec91	ec92	ec93	ec94	ec95	ec96	ec97	ec98	ec99	ec9a	ec9b	ec9c	ec9d	ec9e	ec9f
60560	60561	60562	60563	60564	60565	60566	60567	60568	60569	60570	60571	60572	60573	60574	60575
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60576	60577	60578	60579	60580	60581	60582	60583	60584	60585	60586	60587	60588	60589	60590	60591
ecb0	ecb1	ecb2	ecb3	ecb4	ecb5	ecb6	ecb7	ecb8	ecb9	ecba	ecbb	ecbc	ecbd	ecbe	ecbf
60592	60593	60594	60595	60596	60597	60598	60599	60600	60601	60602	60603	60604	60605	60606	60607
ecc0	ecc1	ecc2	ecc3	ecc4	ecc5	ecc6	ecc7	ecc8	ecc9	ecca	eccb	eccc	eccd	ecce	eccf
60608	60609	60610	60611	60612	60613	60614	60615	60616	60617	60618	60619	60620	60621	60622	60623
ecd0	ecd1	ecd2	ecd3	ecd4	ecd5	ecd6	ecd7	ecd8	ecd9	ecda	ecdb	ecdc	ecdd	ecde	ecdf
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ece0	ece1	ece2	ece3	ece4	ece5	ece6	ece7	ece8	ece9	ecea	eceb	ecec	eced	ec ee	ec ef
60640	60641	60642	60643	60644	60645	60646	60647	60648	60649	60650	60651	60652	60653	60654	60655
ecf0	ecf1	ecf2	ecf3	ecf4	ecf5	ecf6	ecf7	ecf8	ecf9	ecfa	ecfb	ecfc	ecfd	ecfe	ecff

ed00 60687															
ed10 60703															
ed20 60719															
ed30 60735															
ed40 60751															
ed50 60767															
ed60 60783															
ed70 60799															
ed80 60815															
ed90 60831															
eda0 60847															
edb0 60863															
edc0 60879															
edd0 60895															
ede0 60911															
edf0 60927															

ee00 60943															
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ee20 60975															
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eeb0 61119															
eec0 61135															
eed0 61151															
eee0 61167															
eef0 61183															
ef00 															

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ef20	ef21	ef22	ef23	ef24	ef25	ef26	ef27	ef28	ef29	ef2a	ef2b	ef2c	ef2d	ef2e	ef2f
61216	61217	61218	61219	61220	61221	61222	61223	61224	61225	61226	61227	61228	61229	61230	61231
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61328	61329	61330	61331	61332	61333	61334	61335	61336	61337	61338	61339	61340	61341	61342	61343
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P-27				8							
P-28					8						
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G-10					8						

G-11					8						
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G-27						16					
G-28								16			
G-29						16					
G-30								16			
G-31								16			
G-32			8								
PxG-1					8						

Appendix C

Base and Compound Akhyats

Base Akhyats

Compound Akhyats

Phono-Semantic Akhyats

Bent Forms

Black and White Forms

